

MANUFACTURING PROCESSES FOR LARGE SPACE STRUCTURES AND FOR SUPPORTING LONG-DURATION HUMAN SPACE MISSIONS

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ABSTRACT

The ambition to expand human presence deeper into the solar system necessitates the development of technologies capable of fabricating, deploying, and maintaining large-scale space structures with minimal Earth-based support. Traditional logistics, reliant on frequent cargo resupply, incur exponentially increasing mass and volume penalties with distance from Earth. For long-duration lunar outposts, orbital missions, and Martian habitats, structures must be compact during launch, mechanically robust when deployed, and manufactured via scalable and adaptable in-situ processes. Composite materials are critical due to their superior strength-to-weight ratios and resistance to fatigue and corrosion. Out-of-autoclave (OoA) manufacturing techniques have emerged as key enablers, reducing production costs and increasing efficiency for large, complex components such as deployable composite booms, which facilitate compact storage and reliable deployment of membrane-supported systems (e.g., solar sails, antennas, reflectors). The integration of OoA methods with advanced materials promises transformative advances in space structure manufacturing. Concurrently, in-space manufacturing (ISM), including fused filament fabrication (FFF) 3D printing, enables on-demand production and customization of mission-critical components, decreasing dependency on Earth resupply. This study further shows the use of local material (regolith) into composite filaments suitable for FFF printing, enabling a closed-loop material lifecycle aboard space habitats. By combining ultra-thin composite booms with in-situ recycling and additive manufacturing, a sustainable, modular approach to structural maintenance and fabrication for long-duration missions on the Moon and Mars can be realized. This work presents ongoing research on OoA and ISM process development using novel materials to advance sustainable space exploration architectures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ambitions to extend human presence deeper into the solar system are driving exceptional interest in technologies that can produce, deploy, and maintain large-scale structures in space using only minimal support from Earth. Conventional logistics chains, heavily reliant on cargo resupply, impose steep mass and volume penalties which grow exponentially with distance from Earth. For future lunar outposts, long-duration orbital missions, and Martian bases, the solution must involve structures that are compact during launch, robust when deployed, and manufactured using processes that are scalable and flexible enough to be adapted on site.

Composite materials are essential in the development of advanced space structures due to their excellent strength-to-weight ratios and resistance to fatigue and corrosion. These properties enable the

creation of lightweight yet robust components for aerospace applications, driving the need for cost-effective and scalable manufacturing methods. Out-of-autoclave (OoA) processes have emerged as a key solution, offering reduced production costs, improved efficiency, and flexibility, particularly for large, complex components [1,2]. A key application is the production of deployable composite booms, which help solve storage issues in launch vehicles and enable the deployment of large-scale structures in space. Boom structures are slender, elongated components that play a critical role in aerospace applications, particularly in the deployment and stabilization of membrane-based systems such as solar sails, antennas, and reflectors [3-5]. These structures are responsible for maintaining the desired geometry of the membrane throughout its operation, ensuring both precision and reliability.

Given the harsh conditions of the space environment, there is a pressing need for novel materials that offer enhanced durability and resilience. For instance, polymeric nanocomposites, enhanced by nanoparticles like carbon nanotubes and graphene, offer superior properties, including thermal and radiation protection, impact resistance, and enhanced mechanical performance [6-8]. These materials are adaptable to meet the specific demands of space missions, providing lightweight, multifunctional solutions. By integrating OoA manufacturing techniques with these advanced materials, the aerospace industry stands to achieve significant breakthroughs in the design and deployment of next-generation space structures.

In parallel, additive manufacturing, including 3D printing, is revolutionizing space manufacturing. This technique allows for precise customization of components and has already demonstrated its utility aboard the International Space Station (ISS) for in-situ production of tools and parts [9-11]. It allows precise customization of components and can enable the construction of habitats and infrastructure on lunar or Martian missions using local materials or recycled hardware [12-18]. Crewed missions generate streams of single-use packaging, especially in the form of food and drink containers [16-18]. These multilayer laminates, often combining LDPE, PET, and aluminium foil, present a recycling challenge on Earth, but in space, they become both a burden and an opportunity. Every gram of waste that can be repurposed into new functional feedstock eases the mass budget for resupply launches.

Both OoA and in-space manufacturing (ISM) share principles of reducing material waste and optimizing resource utilization, which are crucial for space-based operations with limited resources. OoA allows for large components without autoclave size constraints, while ISM eliminates payload limitations for constructing massive space structures. Together, advancements in composite material fabrication, OoA processes and 3D printing represent a paradigm shift in space structure manufacturing, fostering more efficient, sustainable, and scalable solutions for space exploration.

This study contributes to the expanding body of research aimed at advancing out-of-autoclave (OoA) manufacturing techniques for large-scale structures, while also exploring in-situ process technologies based on fused filament fabrication (FFF). Structural components, such as those used to deploy sensors or reflect sunlight for propulsion, can be produced in modular sections via OoA methods. When damage occurs, for example when a hinge fails or a clip snaps, discarded materials from daily operations may be shredded, reprocessed, and reprinted into functional replacements.

In this closed-loop framework, material science, structural engineering, and mission logistics intersect to create a model of sustainable space exploration. The work presented aims to highlight current research on the development of OoA and in-situ manufacturing techniques, emphasizing the use of novel materials for the construction of space structures and components intended for extended human missions on the Moon and Mars.

2 DEPLOYABLE STRUCTURES

Deployable boom structures are predominantly manufactured using carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg systems, commonly processed via autoclave curing or vacuum bag molding techniques [19–22]. While prepreps offer the advantage of precise resin control, ensuring consistent fiber wet-out and enhanced quality assurance, they inherently limit the diversity of fabric architectures that can be utilized. This limitation reduces design flexibility, particularly when optimizing mechanical properties or conformability for specific structural demands. In contrast, dry fiber reinforcements do not require refrigeration and possess a longer shelf life, thereby simplifying storage and handling logistics. Their cross-sectional geometry varies depending on specific functional requirements. Among the most

prevalent configurations, are storable tubular extendible members (STEM), collapsible tubular masts (CTM), and triangular rollable and collapsible (TRAC) booms. In the present work, the focus is directed specifically toward the fabrication of the A STEM configuration.

This study employs spread tow carbon fabrics combined with CYCOM® 823 epoxy resin. The resin was selected for its favourable viscosity at processing temperatures and its robust mechanical performance once cured.

Spread tow fabrics exemplify how incremental advancements in material architecture can unlock performance gains unattainable with conventional woven textiles. By unbundling standard fiber tows into flat tapes with highly aligned filaments, these reinforcements minimize void content and matrix-rich zones, enabling lighter and stiffer laminates at equivalent fiber volume fractions. When integrated into boom structures, spread tow tapes enhance bending stiffness and foldability, two properties often in competition in traditional woven laminates. During folding and subsequent re-extension, the laminate must endure repeated strain cycles without initiating cracks or causing fiber misalignment, a challenge that intensifies as the laminate thickness decreases to sub-millimeter scales.

The fabrication of ultrathin booms using spread tow composite technology necessitates meticulous control throughout the manufacturing process. This investigation utilizes TeXtreme® HS40 carbon fiber fabrics, featuring 12K filaments and an exceptionally low areal weight of approximately 42 g/m². Such reinforcements facilitate the production of extremely thin laminates while preserving high in-plane stiffness and excellent drapability. The lay-up procedure begins with precision cutting of fabric plies, employing custom-designed jigs to maintain strict $\pm 45^\circ$ fiber alignment. This orientation promotes optimal shear resistance during deployment and retraction cycles, which is critical for boom structures that transition from a coiled stowed configuration to a fully deployed state without suffering permanent deformation or fiber misalignment.

2.1 Fabrication of tubular extensible members

The hand lay-up technique is performed on a stainless-steel cylindrical mandrel, which acts both as a support and as a form to replicate the final tubular mast geometry. Special care is given to the manual impregnation of the carbon fabric with CYCOM® 823 epoxy resin. The resin is degassed in a Thinky ARE-250 planetary mixer prior to use, ensuring that no entrapped air pockets compromise the laminate's structural integrity. A thin film of PTFE, such as Teflease MG2, lines the mould to facilitate clean demoulding and preserve the surface finish, which is especially important in the context of structures that must withstand dynamic deployment loads. To achieve a fiber volume fraction V_f of approximately 60% in the final boom structures, an experimental investigation was carried out on various stacking sequences of auxiliary materials. Many boom samples were produced and analyzed to determine their resin content. To this end, different combinations of release films, both perforated and non-perforated, and varying numbers of peel ply layers were considered to regulate the amount of resin expelled from the composite part and thereby attain the desired V_f . The final process lay-up sequence identified as optimal for this specific laminate consists of the following: an initial layer of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) tape serving as a release layer from the mold surface, followed by the composite laminate itself, then a wrap of Hi-Shrink Tape, a peel ply layer, a perforated Teflon film, a breather layer, and finally the vacuum bag. This optimized stacking arrangement is illustrated schematically in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Consumable layer stacking sequence.

The mold used in this study (Figure 2) was specifically designed for the present application and

manufactured in stainless steel. It features a central through-hole along its longitudinal axis, allowing for the integration of thermal control actuators. One of the main challenges in the fabrication of composite booms, as opposed to flat laminate specimens, is the demolding process, i.e., the separation of the cured part from the mold surface. Typically, a release agent is applied to the mold to facilitate this operation. For the present application, the most suitable release material was identified as Teflease MG2, a polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) tape coated with a silicone-based adhesive. The use of this release system avoids potential chemical contamination of the resin caused by volatile compounds that may be generated during curing because of residual chemicals from conventional liquid release agents. Such volatile substances, if trapped within the laminate, could outgas once in orbit, posing a risk to both structural integrity and spacecraft subsystems. Moreover, this tape is easy to apply and does not require special safety precautions for operator health. In addition to ensuring reliable release of the cured composite from the mold, the Teflon tape also protects the mold surface from potential damage that may occur during demolding. Its use contributes to preserving the integrity of the mold and allows for an excellent surface finish of the final prototype. The lay-up of both the composite material and the consumable layers can be carried out directly on the cylindrical mold. The process begins with the placement of the first layer of dry fabric onto the mold surface. At this stage, difficulties were encountered due to the limited dimensional stability of the dry fabric, which tends to shift or deform when un-impregnated. To address this issue, a thin layer of resin was applied to the mold prior to laying down the fabric. This pre-coating promotes better adhesion between the fabric and the mold, stabilizing the positioning of the first ply.

Figure 2. a) Detail of the mold surface covered with Teflease MG2 and the heating element; b) close-up of the fabric lay-up phase.

Figure 3. Application of the heat-shrink Hi-Shrink Tape; process configuration during the curing stage

Once laid up, the laminate stack is consolidated under vacuum. Breathers and perforated release films ensure that excess resin is evenly distributed and vented, minimising localised resin-rich zones which could otherwise act as failure points. After bagging, the assemblies undergo an OoA curing cycle, ramping from ambient to approximately 125–130 °C, maintaining a hold sufficient to complete the cross-linking reaction throughout the entire thickness (Figure 3). The final cured booms demonstrate minimal residual stress and excellent geometric fidelity. Despite the apparent simplicity of this process, each step embodies critical decisions that reflect the lessons learned from recent experimental campaigns on deployable structures for solar sails and high-area-to-mass-ratio devices [23-24]. To investigate the influence of key process variables, a series of prototypes was manufactured. The study focused on different laminate ply lay-up techniques, variations in consumable stacking sequences, and the selection

of cutting and sanding tools. The results of this experimental campaign, combined with detailed inspections of the fabricated components, informed the development of the processing procedure described earlier. Several representative prototypes were selected for analysis, as their post-process inspection provided critical insights that guided the refinement of the manufacturing methodology. Among the factors examined, particular emphasis was placed on the application of Hi-Shrink Tape, due to its significant impact on part quality and dimensional stability. Figure 4 illustrates two exemplar cases: on the top, a prototype produced without Hi-Shrink Tape; on the bottom, a counterpart fabricated with its use.

Figure 4. Top: 4-m prototype manufactured without heat-shrink tape. Bottom: 4-m prototype manufactured with heat-shrink tape.

Initially, a non-perforated Hi-Shrink tape was employed. While this version provided excellent compaction during curing, the resulting composite structure exhibited a degree of brittleness. Although the component retained its intended shape in the unrolled (production) configuration, it could no longer be rolled without fracturing due to an excessive accumulation of surface resin. To address this issue, a perforated Hi-Shrink tape was subsequently adopted. This alternative not only compacted the boom structure effectively but also facilitated the evacuation of excess resin during curing. The combined effect of improved compaction and controlled resin bleed led to a significant reduction in both thickness and weight of the prototype component. Specifically, the thickness decreased from 0.24 mm to 0.14 mm, as shown in Fig. 5, while the weight was reduced from approximately 20 g/m to 15 g/m.

Figure 5. Thickness of the prototype manufactured without hi-shrink tape and with hi-shrink tape (right).

The reduction in laminate thickness corresponds to an increase in the fiber volume fraction V_f . This increase not only enhances the mechanical performance of the composite due to the greater contribution of the reinforcing fibers but also reduces the tendency of the structure to exhibit brittle behavior. In fact,

a resin-rich laminate would be more prone to matrix cracking during rolling and unrolling operations, eventually leading to composite failure. Furthermore, the reduced laminate thickness results in a more compact rolled configuration of the prototype (Fig. 6), thereby decreasing the overall volume and mass of the associated storage and deployment systems.

Figure 6. Prototype volume in rolled configuration: without Hi-Shrink Tape (left) and with Hi-Shrink Tape (right).

3 IN SITU MANUFACTURING

In-space manufacturing (ISM) refers to the production of components and structures directly in the space environment, rather than on Earth. It enables on-demand fabrication using local or recycled materials, reducing launch mass and mission costs. ISM supports adaptability and self-sufficiency in long-duration missions. It is a key enabler for sustainable space exploration and habitation.

In our studies, the material selected as the basis for studying in-situ manufacturing processes was low-density polyethylene (LDPE). Its hydrogen-rich composition offers inherent radiation shielding properties, particularly effective for neutron attenuation. This characteristic makes LDPE a suitable matrix for combination with high atomic number (Z) elements, enabling the fabrication of structural materials with enhanced shielding capabilities [12, 25-26]. In addition, the polyethylene is present in many elements presented on-board and it is one of the material of the astronaut food packaging [14,18]. The polymer matrix employed in this study was low-density polyethylene (LDPE) powder, supplied by Thermo Scientific Chemicals. The LDPE powder exhibited an average particle size of approximately 500 microns. The Martian regolith simulant (RE) was Biolit powder.

3.1 Fused filament fabrication for in-situ regolith/polyethylene composites

The process begins with the fabrication of composite pellets, which serve as the primary feedstock for the extrusion phase. These pellets were formulated by combining low-density polyethylene (LDPE) with varying weight percentages (5, 10, 15, 20, and 30 wt%) of Martian regolith simulant, acting as the reinforcing filler. Once prepared, the composite pellets were fed into a filament extruder (Felfil Evo), where they were melted, homogenized, and extruded into continuous filaments with controlled diameter and mechanical properties. The extrusion was carried out using a 1.75 mm nozzle at approximately 160 °C, with a screw rotational speed of 7 RPM. These parameters were carefully controlled to ensure consistent mixing and uniform filament quality—critical factors in maintaining dimensional stability and mechanical performance in the final printed parts.

To further enhance the dispersion of filler particles within the polymer matrix, the initially extruded filaments were shredded into smaller fragments and re-extruded. This additional processing step facilitated a more uniform distribution of the regolith simulant, minimized the formation of agglomerates, and consequently improved the structural and functional properties of the composite material.

Achieving the right balance between flexibility and rigidity in LDPE/regolith composite filaments is critical to ensuring both printability and mechanical reliability in fused filament fabrication (FFF) processes. While LDPE inherently offers low melting temperatures and good flexibility, favorable characteristics for extrusion, the addition of regolith simulant at high concentrations, such as 30 wt%,

tends to increase brittleness and reduce ductility. These changes can result in filament breakage, feeding instability, or inconsistent extrusion during the printing process.

Following extrusion and refinement, the filaments were spooled and prepared as feedstock for FFF-based 3D printing, enabling the in-situ fabrication of functional components in space environments. As illustrated in Figure 7a, a 20-meter-long filament containing 30 wt% filler content was successfully wound onto the spool, exhibiting adequate flexibility for handling and processing. Figure 7b highlights the tension applied to the filament during the spooling phase in the cooling stage, which is crucial for maintaining a consistent diameter and preventing deformation.

Figure 7. a) 20-meter-long LDPE/regolith composite filament with 30 wt% filler content wound onto the spool at the end of the extrusion process; b) view highlighting the filament tension during the spooling process in the cooling phase.

After the extrusion process, the LDPE/regolith composite filaments were used to fabricate test elements via fused filament fabrication (FFF), with process parameters carefully optimized to ensure print quality and dimensional accuracy. Figure 8 shows the 3D-printed specimens prepared for dynamic mechanical analysis.

Figure 8. 3D-printed specimens of LDPE/RE composites at 5 wt% (left) and 30 wt% (right) of filler.

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the feasibility of fabricating deployable ultrathin composite boom structures and radiation-shielding materials using both traditional out-of-autoclave (OoA) and in-situ manufacturing (ISM) processes. For structural applications, the integration of spread tow carbon fiber

fabrics with a carefully optimized OoA lay-up and curing cycle enabled the production of high-performance, sub-millimeter-thick tubular booms with excellent stiffness-to-weight ratios, geometric fidelity, and foldability. The use of perforated Hi-Shrink Tape proved particularly effective in improving laminate compaction, reducing resin-rich zones, and enhancing both mechanical robustness and stowability of the final components.

Parallel efforts in the field of in-situ resource utilization focused on the development of LDPE/regolith composite filaments for additive manufacturing. The results highlight the importance of controlling filler dispersion, filament homogeneity, and mechanical flexibility to ensure reliable extrusion and printing performance in the context of fused filament fabrication (FFF). Filaments containing up to 30 wt% regolith simulant were successfully extruded, reprocessed for improved dispersion, and used to fabricate 3D-printed specimens with promising structural integrity. These findings support the viability of in-situ manufacturing strategies based on locally sourced or recycled polymers and regolith, offering a scalable pathway toward self-sustaining construction and maintenance capabilities in extraterrestrial habitats.

Together, these two experimental directions underscore the critical role of advanced material processing, both terrestrial and space-based, in enabling lightweight, deployable structures and functional components for future space exploration missions.

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